

***Facicoris fax* Kiritschenko & Scudder, a genus and species new for Cyprus and Europe (Heteroptera: Rhyparochromidae)**

MANUEL BAENA¹

¹ Plaza Flor del Olivo, 4, bl.7, 1B, 14001, Córdoba, Spain; e-mail: tiarodes@gmail.com

² PO Box 25584, 1310 Nicosia, Cyprus; e-mail: demetriskol@gmail.com

Abstract. *Facicoris fax* Kiristshenko & Scudder, 1973 is recorded for the first time in the island of Cyprus. It is also the first record of this genus and species from Europe. Some details of the morphology, habitus photographs, and distribution maps are given. Details of the places where this species was captured are also included.

Key words: Hemiptera, *Facicoris fax*, female genitalia, distribution, biology, new country record, new continent record.

Introduction

The main works about the Cyprian fauna of Heteroptera are the publications of Håkan Lindberg based on the expeditions made to Cyprus in the year 1939 by the Finnish entomologists Harald, Håkan and P. H. Lindberg (Lindberg 1948a, b). The interest in the fauna of Cyprus has continued until now and there are several papers describing new species, mainly Miridae (Wagner 1953, 1961, 1967, 1968a, 1968b, 1974; Önder 1974; Carapezza 1998; Pagola-Carte & Matocq 2018;), or dealing about new records from the island (Hoberlandt 1952; Linna-vuori 1992; Carapezza 1998; Protić 2007; Quetglas et al. 2012; Gözüaçik & Konuksal 2019).

The alien species have also attracted the attention of the entomologists who have been informed about the colonisation of Cyprus by many of the alien species detected in Europe (Hadjiconstantis & Davranoglou 2018; Davranoglou et al. 2021; Demetriou et al. 2023; John & Kolokotronis 2023; van der Heyden 2023). The most recent catalogue of the Heteroptera of Cyprus, currently outdated, was published by Georghiou (1977).

In this paper, a poorly known genus and species of Rhyparochromidae, *Facicoris fax* Kiritschenko & Scudder, 1973, so far known only in four localities from Central Asia and one from the Near East, is recorded for the first time in Cyprus and Europe. A colour figure of habitus, distribution maps of the species, details of female genitalia and biological notes are also included.

Material and methods

The maps from Google Earth (<https://www.google.pl/intl/pl/earth/>) were used for preparing the distribution maps of *F. fax* (Figs. 3A–B).

Female genitalia were immersed in a commercial dishwasher, cleaned with distilled water and mounted in DMHF on an acetate label. The photos were taken using a Nikon Labophot microscope with a Nikon DS Fi1 Digital camera with a Nikon Ds U2 Control Unit, using Imaging Software NIS-Elements F 2.20.

Figure 1. Original illustration of the female holotype of *Facicoris fax* (drawing by Arthur Smith). Drawing courtesy of the Spencer Entomological Collection, Beaty Biodiversity Museum, UBC.

Results

Facicoris fax Kiritshenko & Scudder, 1973 (Figs 1–2)

The genus *Facicoris* Kiritshenko & Scudder, 1973 is a member of the tribe Gonianotini close to *Pionosomus* Fieber; it can be easily separated by its habitus and other anatomical characters (Péricart 1999). It is a monotypic genus with a single species, *F. fax* Kiritshenko & Scudder 1973 that was described on the basis of a short series of specimens collected in Armenia, Tajikistan and Turkmenistan (Kiritshenko & Scudder 1973). Gidayatov (1982) added a new record from Azerbaijan and Linnavuori (1986) recorded the species from Jerusalem (Israel).

The complete description of *F. fax* has included an excellent figure of habitus (Fig. 1) but no details of the male or female genitalia. Linnavuori (1986) figured only the paramere; however, the female genitalia have been undescribed to date. The spermatheca of this species is S-shaped, and the distal part of the spermathecal duct widens to the end where its diameter is more than twice that of the proximal part; the bulb is hemispherical, somewhat narrower than the end of the spermathecal duct (Fig. 2B). The shape of the ovipositor is presented in Fig. 2C.

Figure 2. *Facicoris fax*. A. habitus, dorsal view (photograph: Christodoulos Makris). B. spermatheca, scale bar: 0,2 mm.; C. ovipositor, scale bar: 1 mm.

Figure 3. Distribution of *Facicoris fax*. A. world distribution; white points represented literature records; red points represented the new records in Cyprus. B. Cyprian localities.

Figure 4. Locality of Kyrenia. A. general view. B. collection site of *Facicoris fax*.

Material studied

CYPRUS: Kyrenia Mountains, dirt road to Palaiosofos (Malatya), 35.315223, 33.202540, 19.11.2023, 1 ex., D. Kolokotronis leg., 612 m., inside a shell of *Eobania vermiculata* (Müller, 1774) (Fig. 4A–B); Kourio, 34.669210°, 32.875403°, 104 m., 24.3.2008, 1 ex., under a piece of wood, C. Makris leg., det. and col.; Panagia, 34.920964°, 32.626315°, 805 m., 24.3.2008, on a winery veranda, C. Makris leg., det. and coll.

Distribution

F. fax is known in the following countries and localities: Armenia (Irvezh), Tajikistan (Khochildiyor, Gissar district), Turkmenistan (valley Mielmi S.E. from Firyuza) (Kiritshenko & Scudder 1973), Azerbaijan (Şeki) (Gidayatov 1982); Israel (Jerusalem) (Linnavuori 1986) (Fig. 3A). Now it is recorded also from Cyprus (Fig. 3B).

Biology

The biology of the species is poorly known; Gidayatov (1982) mentioned collecting specimens under *Thymus sipyleus* Boissier, 1844 (= *Thymus rariflorus* K. Koch, 1849) (Lamiaceae) and *Stipa* sp. (Poaceae) on a summit with very poor vegetation. The specimen of Kyrenia has been discovered in a diverse and ecologically rich habitat characterised by the region's unique topography and climatic conditions due to its steep elevation and its high humidity due to being near the seacoast with northern exposure. The area is characterized by steep slopes, rocky outcrops, and crevices of mostly crystalline limestone. Still, occasionally, there are small grasslands with old ruins of houses and a church. The climate is typically Mediterranean, with hot, dry summers and mild, wet winters. The trees and shrubs of the zone mainly include *Cupressus sempervirens* Linnaeus, 1753 and *Pinus brutia* Tenore, 1815, together with *Quercus coccifera* Linnaeus, 1753, *Ceratonia siliqua* Linnaeus,

1753, *Pistacia terebinthus* Linnaeus, 1753, *P. lentiscus* Linnaeus, 1753, *Crataegus azarolus* Linnaeus, 1753, *Olea europea europaea* Linnaeus, 1753 and some *Arbutus andrachne* Linnaeus, 1762 in the surrounding area. Low vegetation and bushes would include, *Cistus* spp., *Salvia fruticosa* Miller, 1768, *Calicotome villosa* (Poiret) Link, 1806, *Phagnalon rupestre* (L.) De Candolle, 1836, *Sarcopoterium spinosum* Spach, 1836, and some *Thymbra capitata* (L.) Cavanilles, 1803. The habitat at Kourio is *Juniperus* shrubland with stands of *C. sempervirens* and *P. lentiscus*. The third specimen studied was found in the yard of a winery on the outskirts of the village Panagia next to abandoned crops and shrublands with *Q. coccifera* and *P. terebinthus*. The adults of *F. fax* have been collected in different months of the year: February to April, June, August, and November, and the species hibernates in the adult stage.

Conclusions

Facicoris fax is an interesting and poorly known species that was recorded here for first time on the island of Cyprus and in Europe. The Cyprian and World distribution of the species are mapped and the few data about his biology are compiled. The female genitalia are figured for the first time.

Acknowledgements

We are very grateful to Christodoulos Makris for lending us the excellent photo of *Facicoris fax* that illustrates this work, as well as the data of the specimens of his collection. We are very grateful also to Karen Needham, Curator Spencer Entomological Collection, Beaty Biodiversity Museum, University of British Columbia, Canada, for permits us to use the original drawing of the figure of the Holotype of *Facicoris fax* published in Kiritshenko & Scudder (1973).

References

- Carapezza A. 1998. New species and new records of Heteroptera from Cyprus (Insecta). *Atti dell' Accademia roveretana degli Agiati* **248** (VII, 8, B): 29–40.
- Davranoglou L.-R., Cheiladakis N., Makris Ch. 2021. First record of the broad-headed bug *Nemausus sordidatus* (Stål, 1858) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Alydidae) from Greece and Cyprus. *Israel Journal of Entomology* **51**: 1–6.
- Demetriou J., Makris Ch., & Davranoglou L.-R. 2023. First record of *Thaumastocoris peregrinus* (Hemiptera, Thaumastocoridae) in Cyprus. *Travaux du Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle "Grigore Antipa"* **66**: 135–141.
- Demetriou J., Radea C., Peyton J.M., Groom Q., Roques A., Rabitsch W., Seraphides N., Arianoutsou M., Roy H.E., Martinou AF. 2023. The Alien to Cyprus Entomofauna (ACE) database: a review of the status of alien insects (Arthropoda, Insecta) including an updated species checklist, discussion on impacts and recommendations for informing management. *NeoBiota* **83**: 11–42. <https://doi.org/10.3897/neobiota.83.96823>
- Georghiou G.P. 1977. *The Insects and mites of Cyprus*. Benaki Phytopathological Institute, Athens, 347 pp.
- Gidayatov D.A. 1982. *Heteroptera of the group of Pentatomomorpha of Azerbaijan*. Elm, Baku, 159 pp. [in Russian].
- Gözüaçik C., Konuksal A. 2019. Investigations on Heteroptera (Hemiptera) Species in Cereal Agroecosystem of Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus. *Institute of Natural and Applied Science Journal* **12**: 56–67.
- Hadjiconstantis M., Davranoglou L.-R. 2018. Confirmed occurrence of *Ploiaria domestica* (Heteroptera: Reduviidae: Emesinae) in Cyprus. *Israel Journal of Entomology* **48**: 63–67.

- Hoberlandt L. 1952. On some Hemiptera-Heteroptera of Cyprus. *Acta Entomologica Musei Nationalis Pragae* **28**: 109–116.
- John E., Kolokotronis D. 2023. First record of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Heteroptera: Reduviidae: Harpactorinae) for Cyprus. *Entomologist's Monthly Magazine* **159**: 59–65.
- Kiritshenko A.N., Scudder G.G.E. 1973. Some new genera and species of Rhyparochrominae (Hemiptera: Lygaeidae) from the Soviet Union, with a key to the genera of Gonianotini, *Journal of Natural History* **7**: 133–151.
- Lindberg H. 1948a. On the insect fauna of Cyprus. I. Introduction. *Commentationes Biologicae* **10(7)**: 3–22.
- Lindberg H. 1948b. On the insect fauna of Cyprus. II. Heteroptera und Homoptera Cicadina der Insel Zypern. *Commentationes Biologicae* **10(7)**: 23–175.
- Linnavuori R. 1986. Heteroptera of Saudi Arabia. *Fauna of Saudi Arabia* **8**: 31–197.
- Linnavuori R. 1992. The *lateralis* group of the genus *Dimorphocoris* Reuter of Greece and the Middle East (Heteroptera, Miridae, Halticini). *Entomologica Fennica* **3**: 215–222.
- Önder, F. 1974. A new species of *Alloeotomus* Fieber (Heteroptera, Miridae, Deraeocorinae) from Cyprus. *Zoologische Mededelingen* **48(3)**: 18–22.
- Pagola-Cardé S., Matocq A. 2018. *Orthotylus* (*s. str.*) *flavonigrum* n. sp. from the Island of Cyprus (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Miridae). *Heteropterus, Revista de Entomología* **18(1)**: 13–19.
- Péricart J. 1999. *Hémiptères. Lygaeidae Euro-Méditerranéens. Systematique, Seconde Partie. Faune de France 84 B. Volume 2. Systématique, Seconde Partie.* Fédération Française des Sociétés de Sciences Naturelles, Paris, 453 pp.
- Protić L. 2007. Family Cydnidae (Insecta: Heteroptera) in the Natural History Museum in Belgrade. *Polish Journal of Entomology* **76**: 143–159.
- Quetglas J., Balvín O., Luèan R.K., Benda P. 2012. First records of the bat bug *Cacodmus vicinus* (Heteroptera: Cimicidae) from Europe and further data on its distribution. *Vespertilio* **16**: 243–248.
- van der Heyden T. 2023. First records of *Tempyra biguttula* Stål, 1874 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Rhyparochromidae) in Cyprus, Greece and Malta. *Journal of the Heteroptera of Turkey* **5(2)**: 219–221.
- Wagner E. 1953. On the Insect fauna of Cyprus. Results of the expedition of 1939 by Harald, Hakan and P.H. Lindberg. X - Nachtrag zur Heteropterenfauna von Zypern. *Commentationes Biologicae* **13(14)**: 1–17.
- Wagner E. 1961. Über einige neue Miriden-Arten aus dem Zoologischen Museum Helsingfors (Hem. Heteropt.). *Notulae Entomologicae* **40**: 112–122.
- Wagner E. 1962. Nachtrag zur Systematik der Gattung *Tuponia* Reut. (Hem. Het. Miridae). *Notulae Entomologicae* **42**: 140–145.
- Wagner E. 1967. Die Untergattung *Compsocerochoris* Reuter, 1876 der Gattung *Phytocoris* Fallén (Heteroptera Miridae). *Notulae Entomologicae* **47**: 127–146.
- Wagner E. 1968a. Zwei neue Miridae von Zypern (Heteroptera). *Notulae Entomologicae* **48**: 113–116.
- Wagner E. 1968b. *Harpocera cypria* nov. spec., eine neue Miridenart von der Insel Zypern (Hem. Het.). *Mitteilungen der Deutschen Entomologischen Gesellschaft* **27**: 9–12.
- Wagner E. 1974. Zwei neue Miriden, *Dichrooscytus inermis* von Cyprus und *Orthonotus creticus* von Kreta (Heteroptera, Miridae). *Beaufortia* **21**: 165–171.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License
<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Received: 8 July 2024

Accepted: 13 September 2024